

MORPHOLOGICAL STUDY OF THE ENDOMETRIUM IN WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE WITH ABNORMAL UTERINE BLEEDING

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Abstract.

Among gynecological problems, one of the central places is occupied by bleeding from the uterus [3]. The incidence of menometrorrhagia in women of reproductive age is about 22% [1,2].

Despite the improvement of treatment methods, in recent years there has been an increase in the incidence of AUB, which is associated with an increase in the number of women suffering from metabolic diseases, an increase in the number of chronic somatic pathologies, an increase in diseases leading to disorders of the immune system, as well as an unfavorable environment[5].

Keywords: abnormal uterine bleeding, diagnostic papel biopsy, reproductive age, diagnosis, hysteroscopy.

INTRODUCTION

Due to the uncertainty of individual pathogenetic mechanisms, the presence of contraindications to hormonal therapy, relapses of the disease, the often negative attitude of patients towards hormonal therapy and radical surgical methods, as well as the trend of organ preservation in modern medicine, an in-depth study of the pathogenesis of these conditions and the abnormal uterus is required, and the development of new approaches to diagnosis and treatment of bleeding (7,11). According to the literature, up to 65% of women of reproductive age seek medical help for heavy menstrual bleeding, and every tenth consultation with a gynecologist is related to metrorrhagia. AUB today is one of the most serious and unresolved medical problems, which leads to a decrease in the ability to work and quality of life of women, is the main cause of iron deficiency anemia and is the most common indication for urgent hospitalization in specialized gynecological departments of clinical institutes, and also determines its social significance .

Aim of the study. Improving the diagnosis and treatment of women with AUB of reproductive age by determining the morphological structure of the endometrium.

Materials and methods. To achieve the set goals, the study included 85 women of reproductive age who applied to the multidisciplinary clinic of SamSMU on the basis of the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology No. 1. The main group consisted of 54 women with abnormal uterine bleeding, the control group - 31 practically healthy women. The studies were conducted in 2020-2022.

The examination of women includes: determination of clinical and anamnestic features, laboratory diagnostics, assessment of the condition of the pelvic organs using ultrasound, and pipel bilpsy. The criteria for including patients in the study groups were the absence of organic pathology of the urinary system, the absence of acute infectious pathology, specific infection

and sexually transmitted infections [10,15]. Patients with inflammatory pathology in the acute phase or chronic extragenital lesions during the disease period were excluded from the study. All examined pregnant women were of active reproductive age, age range from 26 to 40 years. The average age was 38.1 ± 1.04 years.

Results and discussion. In all 50 (92.59%) patients with endometrial hypertrophy, we conducted a morphological study of the endometrium obtained by the papillary biopsy method. An exception was made by 4 (7.4%) patients, in whom the thickness of the endometrium was from 1 to 6 mm. According to histological examination, 17 (34%) patients had endometrial glandular hyperplasia, 1 (2.0%) patient had endometrial glandular hyperplasia with a submucosal myomatous node, 5 (10%) had glandular-cystic endometrial hyperplasia, endometrial polyps - identified in 24 (48%) patients. Atypical endometrial hyperplasia was found in 3 (6%) patients in the histological examination of the endometrium in patients with AUB.

Due to suspicious cases, 9 women were referred to private medical clinic "MedSI" for hysteroscopy. Hysteroscopy was performed based on the accepted standards, and it revealed pathologies not detected by ultrasound and papillary biopsy - synechiae (22%), submucosal myoma (34%), endometrial polyposis (22%) (Fig. 3.14). This case further confirmed that hysteroscopy is the gold standard when abnormal uterine bleeding is observed.

CONCLUSION

Thus, the analysis of the complaints of patients with AUB, gynecological status, ultrasound examination data, and histological examination of papillary biopsy data showed that AUB patients complain of painful and prolonged menstrual bleeding from the uterus compared to the control group, lower abdominal pain was observed more frequently.

Papillary biopsy is a low-cost, non-invasive and easy-to-use method that has shown high efficiency in detecting intrauterine pathology. According to it, 34% of the main group had endometrial glandular hyperplasia, 2% of endometrial glandular hyperplasia accompanied by a submucosal myomatous node, 10% of glandular-cystic endometrial hyperplasia, 48% of endometrial polyps, 6% of atypical hyperplasia. During the study, the effectiveness of papillary biopsy to preserve fertility in women of reproductive age was determined, and an algorithm for diagnosis was developed.

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